

Effects of Watering Regime and Mycorrhizal Inoculation on Growth, Functional and Yield Traits of four rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) varieties

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Abstract:

A screen house experiment was conducted to determine the effects of watering intervals and Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) inoculation on growth, functional trait, grain yield and yield components of four rice varieties. Treatments were 4 x 3 x 2 factorial combination consisting of three indigenous rice (Igbemo, Benue type, Ofada) and improved varieties (Nerica 8), watering regimes at 4-, 8- and 12- day intervals and with or without the application mycorrhizal inoculum. Data collected were shoot and root weights, number of roots per plant and total root length, number of green and senesced leaves at 50% flowering and maturity, seed and panicle weights. Treatment were significant ($P < 0.05$) on some measured growth variables of mycorrhizal inoculated rice plants including plant height, number of tillers and leaves, leaf area and biomass per plant except fresh root weight of rice. A positive influence of Arbuscular mycorrhizal inoculation and 4 – day watering interval on plant growth and panicle and seed weight and 100 seeds weight compared to the non-inoculated and drought (12- day watering interval) were recorded. Inoculated Igbemo variety watered at 4– day intervals were consistently taller in height, had enhanced biomass and number of leaves and tillers. The 4- day watering interval enhanced rice growth which included, number of senesced leaves at 50% flowering and at maturity, number of green leaves at 50% flowering and at maturity, plant height at 50% flowering and biomass, except root length. Treatment effects were significant ($P < 0.05$) on some yield variables of rice which include, seed weight, 100 seed weight (g) and panicle weight. The values of these parameters were significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in Igbemo and Benue varieties and were enhanced by the 4– day watering intervals. Inoculated Igbemo and Benue type watered at 4 – day interval had more seeds, higher seed weights and panicles with or without AMF inoculation compared with other varieties that were watered at 8– and 12– day watering intervals. The interactions between variety, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation significantly enhanced plant height, leaf area, number of tillers and seed yields for Igbemo and Benue variety and number of spikes and spikelets for Ofada and Nerica 8.

Keywords: Rice, indigenous, rhizobium, moisture stress, adaptation, yield

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a major staple food crops in many parts of the world, providing food for more than three billion people in the form of 50 – 80% of their daily calories intake (Khush, 2005). Rice forms a major part of the diet of most Nigerians and by extension, most population in the developing part of the world. Global demand for rice is rising because of population growth, (Dowling *et al.* 1998), however production of rice is being constrained by abiotic (drought) and biotic (pests and diseases) factors. Rice is the most rapidly growing food commodity in demand across Africa but its productivity of its production system is very low in the sub-saharan African countries due in part to poor access to agro-technologies and poor use of external inputs affluence and changing dietary habits (FAO, 2009). The UN/FAO forecasts that global rice production will need to increase by over 40% by 2030 and 70% by 2050 to meet the increases in demand (FAO, 2009). World rice consumption increased 40% in the last 30 years, from 61.5 kg per capita to about 85.9 per capita (milled rice) (FAO, 2009). Several approaches have been made to increase its production including the use of chemical fertilization.

Mycorrhizal are specialized roots-like organisms formed as a result of the symbiotic relationships of certain fungi with the root of higher plants. They are the active component of the soil which promote growth, help in improving soil quality, play a role in the formation of soil aggregates, improves soil structure and activities. Mycorrhizal fungi extend the plant root ability by increasing the absorbing area of roots 100 to 1000 times thereby greatly improving the ability of the soil plant to explore the soil resources (Linderman, 2013). Several studies have shown that inoculation of plants with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi is promising strategy to enhance its growth and nutrition while reducing input use in agriculture (Hol and Cook, 2005; Akhtar and Siddiqui 2007).

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) are obligate symbionts that colonize the roots of most terrestrial plants, which generally benefits from this AMF association through increased plant nutrient uptake, plant growth and survival rates (Hol and Cook, 2005; Akhtar and Siddiqui 2007), and abiotic stresses including salinity and drought (Smith, 1987, Sudova *et al.*, 2007). AMF increases nutrient uptake not only by increasing the surface absorbing area of roots but also releases some powerful enzymes into the soil that dissolve hard-to-capture nutrients., such as organic nitrogen, phosphorus, iron and other tightly bound soil nutrients (Linderman, 2013). Hence, it is important to explore the possibility of utilizing these microbial-symbionts in agriculture, and thus makes it possible to encourage healthy cultural systems by reducing the use of chemical inputs and enhance productivity and eco-system preservation.

Water accounts for large proportion of living weights of plants, for example in some herbaceous species, water forms 70-90% of the fresh organic weight and 40-60% in many woody species. The singular characteristic of soil water which sets it apart from other materials absorbed by plant is that it is not returned in large proportions by the plant but it covers three continuous and intimately interrelated process which are continuous flow of water from soil into the root hair, the raising of the water through the roots and stems to the leaves and to the growing embryonic tissue and growth points located on the stems and the evaporation of excess water from the leaves to the surrounding environments (Jones and Tardeau, 1997). It is therefore, the medium by which plant nutrients are carried in solution to all parts of the plants as well as the means by which heat is distributed and regulated in plant. The water taken up by the plant from the soil is absorbed only by the young root ends-that is, the root fibrils and hairs-rather than by the whole surface area of the roots (Jones and Tardeau, 1997; Chaves *et al.*, 2012).

Unusual low rainfall, which many scientists agree is due to climate change, is a significant cause of droughts (Kennedy and Cockings, 1997). On the other hand, droughts are becoming longer, harder and more frequent with massive droughts in Africa linked to climate change (Sheffield *et al.*, 2008). Drought is a worldwide constraints affecting crop production by seriously influencing crop production and their yield quality. Drought stress during the rice growth, flowering and terminal stage causes spikelet sterility that leads to unfilled grains (Konstantinos *et al.*, 2006). Also, drought reduces the grain filling period and induces early senescence by redirecting remobilization of assimilates from the straw to the grains. Inadequate water availability limit the increase in dry matter production and yield which is as a result of lack of poor availability of nutrient under water stress. Rhizobium inocula are living culture of bacteria but are mostly sensitive to heat desiccation and light (Jim deacon, 1998; Vadez *et al.*, 2008).

It has been established that yield traits in rice is greatly influenced by management practices (such as irrigation regimes, biofertilizers) among widely adapted indigenous and improved varieties of rice. The aim of this study is to characterize phenotypic responses of rice varieties (local variety and improved variety) to variable soil moisture status and mycorrhizal inoculation. The specific objectives of this research are to examine the effects of watering regime and mycorrhizal inoculation on the (i) seed yield and yield components of indigenous and improved varieties of rice; (ii) identifying stay green traits such as leaf chlorophyll, water soluble carbohydrate contents and leaf senescence among varieties; and (iii) relate the stay green and yield traits in rice to varietal tolerance of soil moisture deficit stress. The findings will be useful in the identification of rice varieties with higher drought tolerance, growth and yield adaptation of the tested rice varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The drought tolerance and yield traits of four rice varieties were studied in the screen house in 2014 / 2015. The study was carried out in the screen house in the Department of Crop, Pest and Soil Management of the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria. Akure lies between lat. 7°16N and long. 5°12E within the rainforest zone of Nigeria with an average annual rainfall of 1500 mm and 30 °C mean temperature.

Experimental design and treatments

The treatments were 4x3x2 factorial combination of rice varieties, watering regimes and mycorrhizal inoculation. The four rice varieties of both local and improved varieties were Igbemo, Ofada, Benue type and Nerica 8 arranged in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four replicates with or without AMF inoculation. Watering regime consisted of application of 1.5 litres of water per pot at 4, 8 and 12 day intervals.

Acquisition of Rice Seeds and AMF Culture

The seeds of local rice varieties (Igbemo, Ofada and Benue) were acquired from Benue, Ogun and Ekiti States while the improved variety (Nerica 8) was acquired from Africa Rice Center, International institute of tropical Agriculture, IITA, Ibadan. A prepared bag of Mycorrhizae inoculant (*Glomus intaradices*) with spores as carrier was obtained from IITA for the experiment.

Planting

The 7 litres capacity perforated pots were filled with 5kg air dried loamy soil and wetted to saturation. Rice seeds were sown at 2-3 seeds per pot. Watering was done equally to attain a uniform germination and establishment of the rice plant, after which the watering treatment began. Weeding was done every 2 weeks during the experiment manually by handpicking.

Extraction of leaf chlorophyll content and determination

Chlorophyll extraction and its determination were done at the Laboratory of the Department of Crop, Soil and Pest Management, Federal University of Technology, Akure. The 2 uppermost leaves of rice plant from each treatment were harvested at 50% flowering. One gramme of the fresh plant samples were cut into pieces and smashed in a mortar. The samples were put in a test tube and its chlorophyll content was repeatedly extracted with successive volume of 100 ml acetone/water (80:20 v/v) until no traces of green color were noticed (residue became white). While adding the solvent (acetone), the test tubes containing the samples were kept boiling in a hot water bath. The total volume of the extract was also recorded at the end of the extraction. Three millimeter (3ml) of the extract was taken and the absorbance was determined with a spectrophotometer (spectronic 20) at two wavelength of 663nm and 645nm that corresponds to maximum absorption of chlorophyll 'a' and 'b' respectively.

Total chlorophyll content was calculated using the following equation derived by Mackinney (1941):

$$\text{Total chlorophyll content (mg/100g tissue)} = (20.2 A_{645} + 8.02 A_{663}) (V/10W)$$

Where, A_{645} = absorbance at 645nm wavelength

A_{663} = absorbance at 663nm wavelength

V = final volume (cm³) of chlorophyll extract in 80% acetone

W = fresh weight (g) of tissue extracted

Determination of water soluble carbohydrate

For determination of water soluble carbohydrate at 50% flowering, 0.5g plant samples were ground and transferred into 250ml test tube and 200ml of water was added. The bottle was capped and shaken on a shaker for about an hour and filtered. 3ml was ejected and the filtrate was retained for the determination of soluble carbohydrate using Anthrone reagents. Concentrated H₂SO₄ 760ml was added to 330ml of distilled water, in addition to 1g of thiourea, 1g of anthrone, stirred until dissolved and was stored in a refrigerator. Glucose stock solution, 1.0g of anhydrous D (+) glucose in water and dilute to one litre prepared immediately before use. From the glucose working standard solutions, 10ml of stock to 100ml was diluted to produce 100ppm. From these, 0, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80 ml was pipetted and made up to 100ml and these produced 0, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80ppm. Samples of 2ml of each glucose working standard solutions were pipetted into the glass test tube and rapidly, 10ml of anthrone reagent was added and mixed by shaking. The test tube was loosely covered with a glass bulb

stopper and placed immediately in boiling water for 20 minutes. The absorbance was measured using spectrophotometer device in a 10mm optical cell at 620nm. The graph of absorbance was plotted against glucose concentration in ppm and prepare standard graph with each batch of extracts examined. The glucose standard becomes 0, 0.8, 1.7, 3.3, 6.7, 13.3ppm respectively.

Examination of Extracts

About 2ml of extracts were pipetted into a test tube. Anthrone 10ml reagent was rapidly added and mixed by shaking and placed in a boiling water bath. The absorbance was measured using a 10mm diameter cuvette.

Data collection on agronomic parameters

Data collection started 8weeks after planting till 18weeks. Eighteen plants used for the growth and yield parameters were randomly selected and tagged on each treatment for proper monitoring and sampling. Data were collected at fortnight intervals on: Number of leaves/ plant and plant height. Observation were made on chlorophyll concentration at 50% flowering, number of tillers/plant, plant leaf area, flag leaf length, onset of flowering, date of 50% flowering. Data were collected on plant parameter at crop harvest which is total shoot weight, total root weight, total number of roots per plant and total root length, panicle weight and 100 seed weight/plant. Plant height was measured using a meter rule from the base of each plant to the tip of the longest leaf. Plant leaf area was calculated from the relation of leaf length to the width using an equation of the form derived by Bartee and. Krieg (1974):

$$\text{Leaf area} = K (L \times W)$$

Where, L = leaf length

W= maximum width and

$$K= 0.75$$

Harvesting

At 90-180 days after planting, matured grains were harvested using scissors to cut off the panicles from the stem. The plant parameters taken on plant biomass at harvest was done by wetting the soil to saturation and gently pouring the soil from the pots and shaking off the soil from the root of the rice plant. This was done so that the plants can be easily uprooted to reduce root breakages and transported to the laboratory for further work. At the laboratory, the following data were taken on the sampled plants per pot: fresh root weight, fresh shoot weight, total number of roots per plant and total root length.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of CRD to test the significance of the treatment using Minitab version 17. The means were separated using Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT).

Results

Effects of variety, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on growth of rice

All the measured growth parameters of rice differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) among the varieties (Table 1a). Igbemo was significantly taller than other varieties before the commencement of flowering and at 50% flowering and before the commencement of flowering. The number of functional green leaves in Benue type at 50% flowering and maturity was significantly higher compared with other varieties. In addition, number of senesced leaves at 50% and at maturity was more for the Benue type. The number of tillers per plant was lowest for Nerica (N-U-8) compared with other varieties. Table 1b shows that, 4- day watering intervals promoted leaf development ($P < 0.05$). Plant height at 50% flowering compared with 8 and 12- day watering intervals while before flowering plant height was not significantly different among the watering regimes. However, the number of functional green leaves/plant was significantly lower for 8- day watering regime, the 4- days and 8- day watering intervals had greater functional green leaves. Number of tillers/plant and of senesced leaves/plant at maturity were significantly greater in rice plants watered at the 4- day interval compared with 8- days and 12 \- day watering intervals. Mycorrhizal inoculation enhanced plant growth irrespective of varieties compared with the non- inoculated plants, plants inoculated with mycorrhizae were significantly taller and had greater leaf area which was significant ($p < 0.05$) over the non- inoculated plants (Table 1c). Rice plants inoculated with mycorrhizae had significantly ($P < 0.05$) greater leaf area compared with the non-inoculated. The number of

green leaves/plant at maturity did not differ significantly between mycorrhized and non-mycorrhized plants but inoculated plants had greater numbers of green leaves/plant than the non-inoculated.

Effects of variety, watering intervals and inoculation on yield and yield components of rice

The result presented in Table 2a shows that the yield and yield components were significantly ($p < 0.05$) different among the varieties. Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed with respect to number of grains yield per plant in Igbemo and Benue type which both had highest grain weight per plant when compared to Ofada and N-U-8. The weight of 100 seeds was significantly higher for Igbemo compared to other varieties. With respect to number of spikelets and spikes, Ofada and N-U-8 had significantly highest number of spikelets compared to other varieties. The number of spikes differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) among varieties. Ofada had the highest number of spikes/plant while N-U-8 had the lowest. Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed amongst the varieties for number of grain yield per plant. Benue type had the highest number of grains per panicle followed by Igbemo and N-U-8 while Ofada had the least number of grain yield per plant. There were significant differences in onset of flowering and days to 50% flowering among varieties. Nerica (N-U-8) had earlier onset of flowering and Ofada flowered late. With respect to 50% flowering, Igbemo and N-U-8 attains 50% flowering earlier while Ofada attains 50 % flowering at later date. Table 2b shows that, watering intervals significantly affected panicle weight. The plants that received 4- day watering intervals had significantly the highest weight of panicle than the other two watering intervals. For 100 seed weight, 4- day watering regime showed significant difference compared with 8- and 12- days watering regimes. The 4- days had the highest number of spikelets and spikes compared with the 8 - day and 12- day watering intervals. The number of seeds/plant in 4- and 8- day watering intervals were significantly higher compared with 12- days watering. Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed with respect to panicle weight and number of spikes between the inoculated and the non- inoculated plants. The inoculated plants had higher panicle weights and number of spikes compared with the non-inoculated plants (Table 2c). There were no significant differences in the number of spikelets and 100 seed weight but the non-inoculated plants had the highest number of spikelets and the highest weight of 100 seeds compared with the inoculated plants. The yield of rice in AMF inoculated plants was 100% higher than that of non- inoculated plants. Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed with respect to number of grains per plant, the mycorrhizal inoculated plants had the highest number of grains per plant. For days to on-set of flowering, significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were observed between the non-inoculated and the inoculated plants.

Interaction between variety and mycorrhizal inoculation on growth and yield of rice

The highest values of shoot weight, total number of roots/plant and fresh root weight/plant were obtained in Benue type while the least values were obtained by N-U-8 (Table 3a) Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were obtained for shoot weight of Benue type over Igbemo and Ofada while N-U-8 had the lowest shoot weight. For root weight, Benue type rice plants had significantly high number and root weight compared with Igbemo, Ofada and N-U-8. Table 3b shows that the effect of watering intervals was significant on total number and weight of roots/plant. The shoot weight for 4- and 8- day watering interval were also significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher compared with 12- day. Although, there were no significant differences for root length among the watering intervals, but 4- day watering intervals had the highest root length compared with 8- and 12- day watering intervals. Table 3c shows that, mycorrhizal inoculation significantly increased the shoot and root growth. The greatest values for these parameters were obtained in rice plant inoculated with mycorrhizal (50% increases) over the non - inoculated plants. Although, differences were not significant on root weight, inoculated plants were greater than the non - inoculated. Inoculated plants also had higher root lengths and total number of roots compared with the non- inoculated plants, although differences were also not significant.

The results show that interactions between variety and mycorrhizal inoculation were significant for most of the parameters measured. Igbemo, a local upland variety had significantly higher stem height before flowering compared with other varieties and watering regimes while N-U-8 had the least. The influence of mycorrhizae inoculation and varieties on leaf area of rice shows that, Igbemo which was inoculated had significantly higher leaf area while Ofada had the lowest. Amongst the non- inoculated varieties, a significant difference was also observed where; Benue type variety had the lowest leaf area. The number of functional green leaves at maturity

and before flowering shows a significant ($P < 0.05$) interaction on mycorrhized rice plants. Benue type had the highest number of green leaves while N-U-8 had the lowest. Although, interaction was not significant for number of tillers but inoculated Benue type still have the highest tillers number, at inoculation, Benue type had highest number of tillers while improved upland variety, N-U-8 had the least. Rice plants that were watered at 4- day intervals and inoculated grew tallest, followed by 8- day watering while mycorrhized plus 12- day watering interval had the lowest before flowering. The leaf area of mycorrhized plus 4 - and 8- day watering regimes were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than for 12- day watering regime. Inoculated rice plants at 4- day watering regime had the highest leaf area while inoculated plus 12 - day watering regime had the least. Amongst the non- inoculated, 8- day watering regimes had the highest leaf area. The interactions between watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation were significant ($p < 0.05$) for number of green leaves/plant at maturity, the rice plant inoculated at 12- day watering interval had the highest number of green leaves. The non-inoculated plants at 4- days watering regime had the highest number of senescence leaves. Amongst, the inoculated watering regime, the number of senesced leaves at 50% flowering and at 12 - days regime had the highest while 8 - days watering regime had the least. The results showed that the yield and yield components were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by the application of bio-fertilizer (Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi). Significant ($P < 0.05$) interaction was observed with respect to weight of panicle inoculated with AMF having the highest in Igbemo while Ofada had lowest weight. However, for 100 seeds weight, a significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher value was obtained for Igbemo. AMF inoculated Benue had the highest mean number of grains per panicle while the non – inoculated Ofada had the lowest. Significant ($P < 0.05$) interactions were observed between varieties and mycorrhizae inoculation on root and shoot weight, total number of roots and root length. For mycorrhized rice plants with respect to root weights, Benue type had the highest and Igbemo had the lowest. Mycorrhized Igbemo had significantly higher root length compared with other varieties. However, with respect to total number of roots and shoot weight, a significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher number of root and shoot weight was observed in Benue type compared with other rice varieties while N-U-8 had the least number of root and shoot weight. For panicle weight of rice, inoculated plants at 4 - day watering interval had the highest value while the inoculated 12 – day watering regime had the lowest. With respect to weight of 100 seeds, inoculated 4 - day had the highest weight of 100 seeds, although, no significant ($P < 0.05$) was observed. The number of spikes and spikelets were not significantly ($P < 0.05$) different amongst the watering regimes and mycorrhizal inoculation. However, mycorrhized plants at 4- days watering interval had the highest number of spikes/plant and spikelets/plant and grain number per plant. Both the inoculated and non- inoculated rice plant at 12 - days watering regime had the lowest grain number per plant.

Interaction between variety and watering intervals on growth and yield parameters of rice.

The interactions between variety and watering regime on rice growth parameters are presented in Table 4a. The results showed that Igbemo rice variety plants that was watered at 4– day intervals, had the highest plant height both at 50 % flowering and before flowering and was significantly different from all other varieties and watering regimes. The improved variety N-U-8 watered at 12- day had the lowest plant height both at 50% and before flowering. Across the varieties and watering intervals, Benue type variety at 4- days watering interval had the greatest number of senesced leaves at maturity and at 50% flowering while N-U-8 had the least. The numbers of functional green leaves at maturity was significantly low in Benue type for 4- days watering at maturity time. Amongst the varieties and watering intervals, with respect to number of leaves before flowering, Benue type variety at 12– days watering intervals had the highest number of leaves which was significant compared with other varieties. Igbemo variety at all levels of watering intervals, had a significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher leaf area followed by N-U-8 at 4- and 8- days watering intervals. For number of green leaves at 50% flowering, Benue type variety irrigated at 4- day and 12– day had the highest number of green leaves/plant when compared with other varieties and watering intervals while N-U-8 at 8- day and 12- day had the lowest number of green leaves. The interactions between rice variety and watering intervals on yields and yield components are shown in Table 4b. Significant ($P < 0.05$) higher weight of panicle in Benue type at 4 days watering regime in terms of 100 seed weights, Igbemo at 4- days watering had the highest mean weight of 100 seeds while Ofada at 8- and 12- days watering had the lowest. Ofada at 4 - days watering intervals had the

highest number of spikes which was significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from other varieties and watering intervals while N-U-8 with watering regime of 12- days had the lowest number of spikes. Although, no significant ($P < 0.05$) interaction was observed with respect to number of spikelets, Ofada at 4- day watering regime had the highest number of spikelets. For days to onset of flowering, N-U-8 at 4- day watering intervals flowers earlier while Ofada at 8- day watering intervals flowers late. With respect to number of grains per plant, Benue type at 4- day watering had significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher values and Ofada at 12- day watering intervals had the lowest number of grains per plant. The interaction between variety and watering regime on plant biomass is shown in Table 4c. The interaction between varieties and watering intervals is significant for shoot weight, total number of roots, root length and root weight. However, Benue type at 8- day watering had the highest number of fresh shoot weight and total number of roots while N-U-8 at 4- 8- and 12- days watering intervals had lesser weight of shoots and total number of roots. There was significant ($P < 0.05$) difference in the root length of varieties at different watering regimes, where, Igbemo at 8- day watering intervals had greater root length. Similarly, in terms of root weight, Benue type variety at 4- day watering intervals had the highest weight of roots while N-U-8 at 12- day watering intervals had the lowest.

Interaction between variety, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on the growth and yield of rice

The interactions between varieties, watering regimes and mycorrhizae inoculation on growth variables and yield and yield components are shown in Table 7. In mycorrhizal inoculated Igbemo rice plants given 4 – day watering intervals had the highest weight of 100 seeds while non- inoculated Ofada given 4 - day watering interval had the lowest. For the weight of panicles, non- inoculated Benue type had the highest value at 4 - day watering intervals. However, there was no significance ($P < 0.05$) interaction for the number of spikelets. Ofada at 4- day watering intervals produced of significantly higher number of spikelets compared with other varieties. For number of spikes, the inoculated variety, N-U-8 at 4 - day watering interval had the highest number of spikes while non- inoculated at 8 - day had the least. The inoculated Benue type given 4 - day watering intervals had the highest number of grains per panicle while inoculated and non- inoculated Ofada given 12 – day watering intervals respectively, had the lowest. The date to onset for the flowering amongst the treatments show that, non- inoculated N-U-8 at 4 day watering flowered earlier while non- inoculated Ofada at 4day watering intervals flowered late.

The Interactions of rice varieties, watering regimes and mycorrhizal inoculation on rice biomass are shown in Table 7c. The results showed that, shoot weight among the varieties responded differently to watering regime and mycorrhizal inoculation. Amongst the varieties, inoculated Benue type given 12 – day watering intervals produced significantly higher weight of shoot than other treatments. Similarly, there was no significant ($P < 0.05$) difference on the root length but inoculated Igbemo given 4 - day watering interval had the highest root length while non- inoculated Benue type at 4 - day watering interval variety had the least. The non- inoculated Benue type had the highest weight of roots and inoculated Igbemo given 12 - day watering interval had the least. The Benue variety given 4 - and 12 - day watering interval had the highest number of roots compared with the inoculated and the non - inoculated N-U-8 which had the lowest root number.

Interactions between rice varieties, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on leaf chlorophyll and water soluble carbohydrate contents.

The interaction of rice varieties, watering regime and mycorrhizal inoculation on leaf nutrient contents as presented in Table 8. A significant ($P < 0.05$) difference was observed amongst the treatment with respect to chlorophyll concentration. Igbemo Inoculated with mycorrhizal and given 12 - day watering interval had the highest chlorophyll concentration (50% increase especially in chlorophyll content of inoculated rice plant over the non – inoculated plants) followed by inoculated Ofada at 4 - day watering interval respectively while non- inoculated Benue variety given 12 - day watering interval had the lowest chlorophyll content. Significant ($P < 0.05$) differences were also observed between varieties, watering regime, mycorrhizae inoculation with respect to water soluble carbohydrate. Non- inoculated Benue type variety at 4- day watering interval had the highest concentration of water soluble carbohydrate when compared with the inoculated treatments and non–inoculated Igbemo had the least concentration of water soluble carbohydrate.

Interactions between rice varieties, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on growth parameters

The interactions between varieties, watering regimes and mycorrhizal inoculation on growth parameters on plant growth are shown in Table 7a. The interactions were Significant ($P < 0.05$) for plant height and at 50% flowering. At 50% flowering, non- inoculated Ofada given 4- day watering intervals produced tallest stem height, followed by non- inoculated Igbemo at 4- day watering intervals compared with other mycorrhizal, variety and watering regimes. However, inoculated Igbemo variety at 4- days watering regime had the tallest plants before flowering which was significantly compared with inoculated and non- inoculated varieties and watering regimes. Benue type of rice inoculated with mycorrhizal and given 4– day watering intervals had the highest number of senescenced leaves/plant while inoculated N-U-8 which was also given 4- day watering intervals lowest number of senescenced leaves/plant. With respect to the number of functional green leaves at maturity, inoculated Benue type at 4- days watering regime maintained the highest number of green leaves while non- inoculated N-U-8 at 8- day watering intervals had the least. Significant ($P < 0.05$) interaction was observed in number of green leaves at 50% flowering, where, the non – inoculated Benue type at 4 day watering intervals had the highest number of green leaves over the inoculated rice varieties. The interaction of rice varieties, watering regimes and mycorrhizal inoculation on number of senescenced leaves at maturity shows that non – inoculated Benue type at with 4 – day interval had the highest number of senescenced leaves while non- inoculated Ofada had the lowest. Across all the treatments, inoculated Igbemo and Benue type varieties at 4 - day watering intervals respectively had the highest number of tillers which were significantly different from other treatments. The leaf area of inoculated Igbemo at 4- day and 8- day watering interval were significantly higher compared with other treatments.

Table 1a: Varietal effects on growth parameters of rice

Varieties	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ maturity /plant
Igbemo	37.06a	75.78a	28.72b	28.67c	4.83b	13.71a	6.38a	10.72ab	34.22c
Benue type	29.56b	66.61b	38.78a	44.17a	10.17a	8.97b	6.72a	12.00a	46.83a
Ofada	30.67b	61.50b	37.17a	36.83b	4.83b	9.36b	6.44a	9.50b	39.67b
Nerica 8	25.06c	55.22c	21.89c	16.56d	4.83b	12.45a	3.38b	4.33c	16.11d

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 1b: Effects of watering intervals on growth parameters of rice

Watering regimes (days)	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ maturity /plant
4	31.50a	69.67a	32.33ab	34.79a	6.42a	12.13a	6.42a	10.67a	37.63a
8	30.25a	64.42ab	28.88b	30.87ab	3.92b	12.19a	5.57b	7.79b	33.63b
12	30.00a	60.25b	33.71a	29.00b	5.96a	9.04b	5.42b	8.96ab	31.38b

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 1c: Effects of mycorrhizal inoculation on growth parameters of rice

Mycorrhizal inoculation	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ maturity /plant
Non – inoculated	29.33a	64.36a	32.72a	32.03a	5.22a	9.87b	5.56a	9.28a	34.42a
Inoculated	31.83a	65.12a	30.56a	31.08a	5.64a	12.38a	5.92a	9.00a	34.00a

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 2a: Effects of variety on yield and yield components of rice

Varieties	Panicle weight (g)	100 seed weight (g)	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets/plant	Grain yield/Plant (g)
Igbemo	4.56a	3.22a	10.67a	112.94b	101.00a
Benue type	4.28a	2.50b	10.06ab	121.56ab	105.94a
Ofada	2.67b	1.94c	11.11a	147.28a	70.56b
Nerica 8	3.37b	2.78ab	9.56b	141.22a	100.89b

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 2b: Effects of watering intervals on yield and yield components of rice

Watering regime (days)	Panicle weight (g)	100 seed weight (g)	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets/plant	Grain yield/ plant (g)
4	4.56a	2.92a	10.54a	136.46a	103.82a
8	3.45b	2.50b	10.38a	135.67a	95.92a
12	3.14b	2.42b	10.13a	120.13a	84.04b

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 2c: Effects of mycorrhizal inoculation on yield and yield components of rice

Mycorrhizal inoculation	Panicle weight (g)	100 seed weight (g)	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets/plant	Grain yield/plant (g)
Non – inoculated	3.59b	2.58a	9.94b	123.86a	87.67b
Inoculated	3.84a	2.64a	10.75a	137.64a	101.53a

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 3a: Effects of variety on rice biomass

Varieties	Fresh shoot weight (g) /plant	Total no. of roots/plant	Root length (cm ²)	Fresh root weight (g)/plant
Igbemo	48.33b	103.17c	19.22a	13.00c
Benue type	69.22a	283.72a	15.94b	42.22a
Ofada	38.61b	157.50c	15.56b	22.22b
Nerica 8	20.89b	56.50d	13.61b	15.00bc

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 3b: Effects of watering intervals on biomass of rice plant

Watering regimes (days)	Fresh shoot weight (g)	Total no. of roots/plant	Root length (cm)	Fresh root weight (g)
4	51.21a	172.83a	15.54a	28.42a
8	47.29a	140.83b	16.67a	22.42b
12	34.29b	137.00b	16.04a	18.50b

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 3c: Effects of mycorrhizal inoculation on biomass of rice plant

Mycorrhizal inoculation	Fresh Shoot weight (g)/plant	Total no of roots/plant	Root length (cm)	Fresh root weight (g)/plant
Non – inoculated	38.22b	143.28a	15.42a	24.89a
Inoculated	50.31a	157.17a	16.75a	21.33a

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 4a: Interactions between variety and watering intervals on growth parameters

Varieties	watering intervals (days)	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ maturity /plant
Igbemo	4	39.67a	80.83a	30.38bc	32.17bc	6.00b	14.43a	7.33a	11.50ab	37.67bcd
	8	35.33ab	74.33ab	27.67bcd	24.00cde	4.00bc	14.58a	6.00ab	10.17b	30.67d
	12	36.17ab	72.17abc	27.67bcd	29.83bcd	4.50bc	12.12a	5.83ab	10.50b	34.33cd
Benue	4	31.00bcd	73.17ab	31.83bc	47.50a	10.83a	9.38ab	7.33a	15.50a	54.33a
	8	28.83bcd	58.83bcd	34.00b	44.83a	6.00b	10.73ab	5.67ab	9.33bc	47.33ab
	12	29.83bcd	67.83abc	50.50a	40.17ab	13.37a	6.80ab	7.17ab	11.17ab	38.83bcd
Ofada	4	30.00bcd	71.50abc	35.83b	40.00ab	6.83b	10.90ab	6.38a	11.83ab	43.33abc
	8	32.17abc	59.33bcd	38.00ab	38.50ab	3.83bc	9.98ab	6.67a	7.17bcd	39.50bcd
	12	27.67bcd	53.67bcd	37.67ab	32.00bc	3.83bc	7.23b	5.83ab	9.50bc	36.17bcd
Nerica 8	4	24.67bcd	53.17cd	30.83bc	19.50de	2.00c	13.80a	4.17bc	3.83d	15.17e
	8	24.67cd	65.17a-d	15.83d	16.17e	1.83c	13.51a	3.17bc	4.50cd	17.00e
	12	22.83d	47.33d	19.00cd	14.00e	1.83c	10.02ab	2.83c	4.67cd	16.17e

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability

Table 4b: Interaction between variety and watering intervals on yield and yield components of rice

Varieties	watering intervals (days)	Panicle weight (g)	100 seed weight (g)	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets /plant	Grain yield/panicle (g)
Igbemo	4	4.67abc	3.83a	10.50ab	110.00a	107.50ab
	8	4.83ab	2.83abc	11.00ab	118.17a	104.83ab
	12	4.17bcd	3.00ab	10.50ab	110.67a	90.67abc
Benue	4	6.50a	2.83abc	9.67ab	118.67a	114.67a
	8	3.00bcd	2.33bc	9.83ab	133.83a	109.33ab
	12	3.33bcd	2.33bc	10.67ab	112.17a	93.83abc
Ofada	4	3.00bcd	3.00ab	12.33a	167.83a	84.67bc
	8	2.67d	1.83c	10.50ab	160.00a	77.00c
	12	2.33d	2.00bc	10.50ab	114.00a	50.00d

Nerica 8	4	4.08bcd	3.00ab	9.67ab	149.33a	108.50ab
	8	3.32bcd	3.00ab	9.67ab	130.67a	92.50abc
	12	2.72cd	2.33bc	8.83b	143.67a	101.67abc

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 4c: Interaction between variety and watering intervals on rice biomass

Varieties	watering intervals (days)	Fresh Shoot weight (g)/plant	Total no. of roots/plant	Root length (cm)	Fresh root weight (g)/plant
Igbemo	4	78.17ab	139.167bc	18.50ab	17.17cde
	8	44.00b-e	89.67bcd	20.50a	15.00de
	12	22.83de	80.67bcd	18.67ab	6.83e
Benue	4	52.50a-d	322.00a	13.83ab	61.00a
	8	82.00a	264.50a	12.17b	34.00b
	12	73.17ab	264.67a	14.83ab	31.67bc
Ofada	4	41.67cde	164.33b	13.17b	21.17b-e
	8	51.67a-d	156.50b	18.17ab	18.83b-e
	12	22.50de	151.67b	15.33ab	26.67bcd
Nerica 8	4	32.50de	65.83cd	16.67ab	14.33de
	8	11.50e	52.67d	15.83ab	21.83b-e
	12	18.67de	51.00d	15.33ab	8.83e

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 5a: Interactions between variety and mycorrhizal inoculation on growth parameters of rice

Varieties	Mycorrhizal Inoculation	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senescenced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senescenced leaves @ maturity /plant
Igbemo	Non – inoculated	35.11ab	76.33a	27.22c	25.44cd	5.33b	12.64a	6.11a	12.11a	32.67c
Igbemo	Inoculated	39.00a	75.22a	30.22abc	31.89bc	4.33b	14.77a	6.67a	9.33a	35.78bc
Benue	Non – inoculated	26.78cd	59.00b	38.44a	48.22a	9.78a	6.02c	6.44a	11.78a	50.00a
Benue	Inoculated	32.33bc	74.2a	39.11a	40.11ab	10.56a	11.92ab	7.00a	12.22a	43.67ab
Ofada	Non- inoculated	30.56bcd	68.44a	37.22ab	38.44b	4.22bc	8.55bc	6.44a	9.11a	41.22b
Ofada	Inoculated	30.78bcd	54.56b	37.11ab	35.22b	5.44b	10.18bc	6.44a	9.89a	38.11bc
Nerica 8	Non- inoculated	24.89d	53.67b	28.00bc	16.00e	1.56d	12.27ab	3.33b	4.11b	13.78d
Nerica 8	Inoculated	25.22d	56.78b	15.78d	17.11de	2.22cd	12.27ab	3.56b	4.56b	18.44d

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability

Table 5b: Interactions between variety and mycorrhizal inoculation on yield and yield components of rice

Varieties	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Panicle weight (g)/plant	100 seed weight (g)/plant	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets/plant	Grain yield/plant (g)
Igbemo	Non – inoculated	4.00a-d	3.33a	11.00a	110.00a	99.67b
Igbemo	Inoculated	5.11a	3.11ab	10.33ab	118.17a	102.33ab
Benue	Non – inoculated	4.11abc	2.44bcd	9.11ab	110.67a	91.78bc
Benue	Inoculated	4.44ab	2.56abc	11.00a	133.83a	120.11a
Ofada	Non- inoculated	2.56d	1.67d	11.22a	112.17a	65.56d
Ofada	Inoculated	2.78cd	2.22cd	11.00a	167.83a	75.56cd
Nerica 8	Non- inoculated	2.70a-d	2.89abc	8.44b	160.00a	93.67bc
Nerica 8	Inoculated	3.04bcd	2.67abc	10.67a	143.67a	108.11ab

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 5c: Interactions between variety and mycorrhizal inoculation on rice biomass

Varieties	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Fresh shoot weight (g)/plant	Total no. of roots/plant	Root length (cm)/plant	Fresh root weight (g)/plant
Igbemo	Non – inoculated	44.56bc	106.11bc	18.78a	14.56c
Igbemo	Inoculated	52.11b	100.22bc	19.67a	11.44c
Benue	Non – inoculated	50.78b	258.00a	12.33b	42.22a
Benue	Inoculated	87.67a	309.44a	14.89ab	42.22a
Ofada	Non- inoculated	39.00bc	162.79b	15.22ab	15.57c
Ofada	Inoculated	38.22bc	152.22b	15.89ab	28.89b
N-U-8	Non- inoculated	18.56c	46.22c	15.22ab	13.00c
N-U-8	Inoculated	23.22c	66.78c	16.56ab	17.00b

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Table 6a: Interaction between watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on growth parameters of rice

Watering intervals (days)	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ maturity /plant
4	Non – inoculated	30.83ab	71.25a	36.58a	35.75a	6.33a	9.57b	6.25ab	11.42a	37.67a
8	Non – inoculated	26.92b	61.83a	29.00ab	30.33ab	4.17b	11.34a	5.33ab	9.92a	34.50a
12	Non- inoculated	30.25ab	60.00a	32.58ab	30.00ab	5.17ab	8.70b	5.08b	6.50b	31.08a
4	Inoculated	32.17a	68.08a	28.08b	33.83ab	6.50a	14.68a	6.58a	9.92a	37.58a
8	Inoculated	33.58a	67.00a	28.75ab	31.42ab	3.67b	13.06a	5.42ab	5.67b	32.75a
12	Inoculated	29.75ab	60.50a	34.83ab	28.00b	6.75a	9.38b	5.75ab	11.42a	31.67a

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability

Table 6b; Interaction between watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on yield and yield components of rice

Watering intervals (days)	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Panicle weight (g)/plant	100 seed weight (g)/plant	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets/plant	Grain yield/plant (g)
4	Non – inoculated	4.56a	2.83a	9.83a	120.92a	89.42bc
8	Non – inoculated	3.21b	2.50a	9.92a	132.17a	91.67bc
12	Non- inoculated	3.11b	2.42a	10.08a	118.50a	81.92c
4	Inoculated	4.67a	3.00a	11.25a	152.00a	118.25a
8	Inoculated	3.70a	2.50a	9.92a	139.17a	100.17b
12	Inoculated	3.17b	2.42a	10.17a	121.75a	86.92c

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability.

Varieties	Watering intervals (days)	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Plant height before flowering (cm)	Plant height @ 50% flowering (cm)	No. of green leaves before flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @50% flowering /plant	No. of green leaves @ maturity /plant	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of tillers /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ 50% flowering /plant	No. of senesced leaves @ maturity /plant
Igbemo	4	Non – inoculated	38.67ab	81.33a	31.67b-g	31.00b-j	7.33b-e	12.50abc	7.00ab	14.67ab	39.67a-e
	8	Non – inoculated	31.33a-d	76.00ab	39.67b-g	22.33f-j	5.33d-g	13.05abc	6.33abc	14.33ab	32.67c-h
	12	Non – inoculated	35.33a-d	71.67abc	20.33d-g	23.00e-j	3.33efg	12.37abc	5.00a-d	7.33b-f	25.67e-i
Igbemo	4	Inoculated	40.67a	80.33a	30.0b-g	33.33a-i	4.67d-g	16.35a	7.67a	8.33a-f	35.67b-f
	8	Inoculated	39.33ab	72.67abc	25.67c-g	25.67d-j	2.67fg	16.10a	5.67a-d	6.00c-f	28.67d-i
	12	Inoculated	37.00abc	72.67abc	35.00a-	36.67a-h	5.67d-g	11.87abc	6.67abc	13.67abc	43.00a-e
Benue	4	Non-inoculated	28.00a-d	71.33abc	34.67a-f	50.67a	10.00a-d	4.90c	7.00ab	14.67ab	56.00a
	8	Non-inoculated	24.67a-d	44.67c	33.00a-g	46.33abc	7.00b-f	8.70abc	5.00a-d	13.00a-d	50.00abc
	12	Non – inoculated	27.67a-d	61.00abc	47.67ab	47.67ab	12.33ab	4.45c	7.33a	7.67b-f	44.00a-d
Benue	4	Inoculated	29.67a-d	75.00abc	29.00b-g	44.33abc	11.67abc	13.85ab	7.67a	16.33a	52.67ab
	8	Inoculated	37.33abc	73.00abc	35.00a-e	43.33a-d	5.00d-g	12.65abc	6.33abc	5.67c-f	44.67a-d
	12	Inoculated	30.00a-d	74.67abc	53.33a	32.67a-i	15.00a	9.15abc	7.00ab	14.67ab	33.67b-f
Ofada	4	Non – inoculated	30.00a-d	83.33a	38.00a-d	41.00a-f	6.33c-g	8.75abc	7.00ab	12.33a-e	43.00a-e
	8	Non – inoculated	27.00bcd	61.00abc	36.00a-e	38.67a-f	3.00efg	9.20abc	6.67abc	8.33a-f	41.00a-e
	12	Non – inoculated	34.67a-d	61.00abc	37.67a-e	35.67a-i	3.33efg	7.70abc	5.67a-d	6.67b-f	39.67a-e
Ofada	4	Inoculated	29.67a-d	59.67abc	33.67a-g	39.00a-f	7.33b-e	13.05abc	6.67abc	11.33a-f	43.67a-d
	8	Inoculated	33.00a-d	57.67abc	40.00a-d	38.33a-g	4.67d-g	10.75abc	6.67abc	6.00c-f	38.00b-e
	12	Inoculated	29.67a-d	46.33bc	37.67a-e	35.67a-i	4.33efg	6.75bc	6.00a-d	12.33a-e	32.67c-g
Nerica 8	4	Non – inoculated	26.67bcd	49.00bc	42.00a-d	39.00a-f	1.67fg	12.13abc	4.00a-d	4.00f	12.00i
	8	Non – inoculated	24.67cd	65.67abc	17.33fg	38.33a-g	1.33g	14.38ab	3.33cd	4.00f	14.33i
	12	Non – inoculated	23.33d	46.33bc	24.67c-g	35.67a-g	1.67fg	10.30abc	2.33d	4.33ef	15.00hi
Nerica 8	4	Inoculated	28.67a-c	57.33abc	17.67d-g	20.33g-j	2.33fg	15.48ab	4.33bcd	3.67f	18.33f-i
	8	Inoculated	24.67cd	64.67abc	14.33fg	14.00j	2.33efg	12.65abc	3.00cd	5.00def	19.67f-i
	12	Inoculated	22.33d	48.33bc	13.33g	13.67j	2.00fg	9.75abc	3.00cd	5.00def	17.33ghi

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability number

Table 7b: Interaction between variety, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on yield and yield components

Varieties	Watering regime (days)	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Panicle weight (g)/plant	100 seed weight (g)/plant	No. of spikes/plant	No. of spikelets /plant	Grain yield/plant (g)
Igbemo	4	Non – inoculated	4.00abc	3.67ab	11.00ab	105.67a	101.67bcd
	8	Non – inoculated	4.33abc	3.00a-d	11.33ab	128.00a	108.00bcd
	12	Non – inoculated	3.67abc	3.33abc	10.67ab	99.67a	89.33b-e
Igbemo	4	Inoculated	5.33abc	4.00a	10.00ab	114.33a	113.33abc
	8	Inoculated	5.33abc	2.67a-d	10.67ab	108.33a	101.67bcd
	12	Inoculated	4.67abc	2.67a-d	10.33ab	122.00a	92.00bcd
Benue	4	Non- inoculated	6.67a	2.67a-d	8.33ab	84.00a	80.67a-e
	8	Non- inoculated	2.33c	2.33a-d	9.00ab	122.00a	99.67bcd
	12	Non –inoculated	3.33bc	2.33a-d	10.00ab	108.33a	95.00bcd
Benue	4	Inoculated	6.33ab	3.00a-d	11.00ab	153.33a	148.67a
	8	Inoculated	3.67bc	2.33a-d	10.67ab	145.67a	119.67ab
	12	Inoculated	3.33bc	2.33a-d	11.33ab	116.00a	92.67bcd
Ofada	4	Non – inoculated	2.67c	2.00bcd	12.67a	154.67a	78.00cde
	8	Non – inoculated	2.67c	1.67cd	10.33ab	158.67a	69.00de
	12	Non – inoculated	2.67c	1.33d	10.67ab	134.33a	49.67e
Ofada	4	Inoculated	3.33bc	2.00bcd	12.00a	181.00a	91.33bcd
	8	Inoculated	2.67c	2.00bcd	10.67ab	161.33a	85.00b-e
	12	Inoculated	2.33c	2.67a-d	10.33ab	93.7a	50.33e
Nerica 8	4	Non – inoculated	4.50abc	3.00a-d	7.33b	139.33a	97.33bcd
	8	Non – inoculated	3.50bc	3.00a-d	9.00ab	120.00a	90.00b-e
	12	Non – inoculated	3.10c	2.67a-d	9.00ab	132.00a	93.67bcd
Nerica	4	Inoculated	3.67abc	3.00a-d	12.00a	159.33a	119.67ab
	8	Inoculated	3.13c	3.00a-d	11.33ab	141.33a	95.00bcd
	12	Inoculated	2.33c	2.00bcd	8.67ab	155.33a	109.67abc

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability

Table 7c: Effect of variety, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation rice biomass

Varieties	Watering regimes (days)	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Fresh shoot weight(g)/plant	Total no. of roots/plant (g)	Root length (cm)/plant	Fresh root weight (g)/plant
Igbemo	4	Non – inoculated	71.00a-e	115.67cd	19.00a	13.33ef
	8	Non – inoculated	49.33b-f	128.33cd	20.00a	22.00c-f
	12	Non – inoculated	13.33f	74.33cd	17.33a	8.33f
Igbemo	4	inoculated	85.33abc	162.67bcd	18.00a	21.00c-f
	8	Inoculated	38.67b-f	51.00cd	21.00a	8.00f
	12	Inoculated	32.33b-f	87.00cd	20.00a	5.33f
Benue	4	Non- inoculated	28.67c-f	296.00ab	11.67a	75.67a
	8	Non- inoculated	86.00ab	352.00a	13.67a	37.33b-e
	12	Non -inoculated	37.67b-f	126.00cd	11.67a	13.67ef
Benue	4	Inoculated	76.33a-e	348.00a	16.00a	46.33bc
	8	Inoculated	78.00a-d	177.00bcd	10.67a	30.67b-f
	12	Inoculated	108.67a	403.3a	18.00a	49.67b
Ofada	4	Non - inoculated	34.67b-f	181.67bc	12.67a	18.00f
	8	Non - inoculated	50.67a-f	165.00bcd	19.00a	19.33def
	12	Non - inoculated	34.67b-f	141.67cd	14.00a	9.33f
Ofada	4	Inoculated	51.67a-f	147.00cd	13.67a	24.33b-f
	8	Inoculated	52.67a-f	148.00cd	18.00a	18.33def
	12	Inoculated	10.33f	161.67bcd	16.67a	44.00bcd
Nerica 8	4	Non – inoculated	24.33def	47.67cd	16.67a	14.00ef
	8	Non – inoculated	12.33f	44.67d	15.00a	16.00f
	12	Non – inoculated	19.00ef	46.33cd	14.67a	9.00f
Nerica 8	4	Inoculated	40.67b-f	84.00cd	17.00a	14.67f
	8	Inoculated	10.67f	60.67cd	16.67a	27.67b-f
	12	Inoculated	18.33ef	55.67cd	16.00a	8.6f

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability

Table 8: Interaction between varieties, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on rice chlorophyll and water soluble content

Varieties	Watering regime (days)	Mycorrhizal inoculation	Chlorophyll concentration	Water soluble carbohydrate
Igbemo	4	Non – inoculated	7.91gh	2.79def
	8	Non – inoculated	6.68j	0.49gh
	12	Non – inoculated	6.08m	0.10h
Igbemo	4	Inoculated	6.93i	3.29ab
	8	Inoculated	5.19o	2.59f
	12	Inoculated	18.05a	3.19a-d
Benue	4	Non- inoculated	8.05g	3.34a
	8	Non- inoculated	6.62jk	0.28h
	12	Non –inoculated	4.04q	2.72ef
Benue	4	Inoculated	7.81h	2.91b-f
	8	Inoculated	4.77p	3.01a-e
	12	Inoculated	12.49c	2.94a-f
Ofada	4	Non – inoculated	7.82h	0.79g

	8	Non – inoculated	8.98f	2.99a-e
	12	Non – inoculated	5.71n	2.69ef
Ofada	4	Inoculated	15.07b	2.71ef
	8	Inoculated	12.37cd	0.33h
	12	Inoculated	6.52kl	3.20abc
NERICA 8	4	Non – inoculated	9.12f	2.89b-f
	8	Non – inoculated	12.24d	2.82c-f
	12	Non – inoculated	5.29o	2.72e-f
NERICA 8	4	Inoculated	6.47l	3.05a-e
	8	Inoculated	11.19e	3.00a-e
	12	Inoculated	6.46l	2.81c-f

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5 % level of probability

DISCUSSION

Effects of variety, watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation on performance of rice

In this study, there were significant differences in the responses of rice varieties to watering regime and mycorrhizal inoculation in terms of growth and yield parameters. This showed that the performances of the rice varieties were influenced by watering intervals and mycorrhizal inoculation. This is showed that rice growth characteristics were affected by status of moisture in its root zone. Reduction in the growth and yields of crops under field or green house conditions due to drought stress or deficit irrigation were reported by Dias *et al.* (2007), Silva *et al.* (2004) and Agele *et al.* (2014). The growth characters of the rice varieties differed significantly between 4- and 12- days watering regimes and mycorrhizal inoculation under 12- day watering (severe moisture stress) the rice plants wilted but recovered following replenishment of root zone moisture.

Effects of mycorrhizal inoculation on growth parameters of rice

The findings from the study showed that rice varieties responded differently to Ambuscular mycorrhizal fungi inoculation. The mycorrhizal inoculated plants had better growth performance compared with the non-inoculated. These results agree with the findings of Sakthivel and Gnanamanickman (1987), Ashrafuzzaman *et al.* (2009), and Ishak *et al.* (2012) that biofertilizers significantly improved rice growth by increasing soil nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus which influenced plant growth and significantly enhanced plant height and photosynthesis rate. Similarly, Chi *et al.* (2005) obtained up to 23-63 % increases in plant height of inoculated rice over the non – inoculated. The authors argued that indole-acetic acid (IAA) and gibberellin production were the key mechanisms for the observed growth improvement. Furthermore, the results of this study also agrees with the findings of Mishra and Sunlia (2000) and Dar and Bali (2007) who stated that application of biofertilizer on rice improved leaf development (number and area of leaves and all yields attributes). The increase in panicles, numbers of tillers and mycorrhizal inoculation could have resulted from efficient nutrient and water uptake via improved root development apart from availability of phytohormones like indole acetic acid and ethylene.

Mycorrhizal inoculated rice plants performed better than non – inoculated in terms of height, number of tillers leaves. The improvement in growth variables is also attributable to increases in soil nutrients such as N and P which influences growth and leads to high photosynthesis rate. Sakariyawo *et al.* (2013) also reported that upland rice inoculated with mycorrhizal fungi were better than the non – inoculated plants. This was attributed to the growth promoting mechanisms of mycorrhizal fungi including the mobilization and efficient uptake of nutrients (Biswas *et al.*, 2000, Khan *et al.*, 2005) and enhancement of stress resistance (Alami *et al.*, 2000, Khalil and El Naema 2012).

With respect to plant biomass, the rice plant inoculated with mycorrhizal fungi exhibited significant performance over the non- inoculated. Mycorrhizal inoculation is known to improve the growth and biomass development of a wide host range including rice due to enhanced efficiency as phosphate solubilizer and transporter (Smith *et al.*, 2003, Khalil and El Naema 2012). The ambuscular mycorrhizae fungi is known to

enhance the absorption of nutrients from the soils which would have move to the roots principally by mass flow, in addition to those which could have diffused through the soil slowly. The beneficial effect on host plant by mycorrhizal infection is usually associated with improved plant nutrition, especially phosphorus and by the virtue of extensive root system that extend the functional mycelium into surrounding soil, making a greater pool of nutrients available for absorption by plant (Lovelock *et al.*, 2004, Guisou, 2009). The increased plant growth, often responded as high as several hundred-fold increases with respect to biomass (Menge, 1983). The positive response observed in mycorrhizal inoculation (in rice plants can be attributed to the promotion of root development and absorption of nutrients (Klein *et al.*, 1990, Shukla *et al.*, 2012). The induction of longer roots with increased number of root hairs is a growth response attributed to IAA production in plants inoculated with biofertilizers which triggers plant growth and vigour, a more productive plants and result by higher yields at maturity.

Effects of watering intervals on growth parameters of rice

The results of this study showed that the measured growth variables of rice responded to watering regimes imposed. The enhancement of height, number of leaves, tillers and green leaves at 50 % flowering and at maturity/plant by more frequent watering (4- days) may be attributed to higher moisture content in the crop root zone. This observation is consistent with reports of Henson *et al.* (2005), Majumder (2010) and Agele *et al.* (2014) which have stated that when adequate water is available, plant cells remain turgid and plants retain their form, structure and function. In addition, Khalil and El-Noemani (2012) and Bahreininejad *et al.* (2013) stated that, water stress reduces plant growth through inhibition of various physiological and biochemical processes such as photosynthesis, respiration, translocation, ion uptake, carbohydrates, nutrient metabolism and hormones. The rice varieties that were watered at 4 days intervals, were taller than those watered fortnightly. This result further confirms how essential water is to growth and development of rice plant, a crop sensitive to water deficit (Henson *et al.*, 2005, kachnoo and Razdau, 2006)

Effects of mycorrhizal inoculation on yield and yield components of rice plant

The positive responses of rice varieties in this study to mycorrhizal inoculation reflected in terms of higher yield and yield components. This suggest effective partitioning of assimilates of biofertilizer treated rice plants. This could be ascribed to the ameliorative effects of mycorrhizae spores on rice in terms of osmoregulation and osmoprotection (Ruiz-Lozano, 2003, Sadova *et al.*, 2007, Shukla *et al.*, 2012) and on soil nutrient availability. Increase in the availability in soil nutrient due to biofertilizer application had singled out phosphorus as the most in availability for uptake was reported by Solaiman and Hirata (1997), which is the most important nutrient requirement for rice plants. The increases in the yield parameters (panicle weight, 100 seed weight, grain yield/panicle, number of spikelets) in response to AMF inoculation can be attributed to its growth promoting ability of AMF such as in the mobilization and efficient uptake of nutrients (Vessey, 2003, Zhang *et al.*, 2012)

Interactions between watering regime and Ambuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi inoculation

In this study, there were significant ($P < 0.05$) interactions of mycorrhizal inoculation and watering regime on growth characteristics which include leaf area, number of senescence leaves at 50% maturity, plant height before flowering and number of green leaves both at maturity and before flowering and on yield of mycorrhized rice plant with respect to grain yield. The watering regime under the 4 - day interval was statistically different to fortnight watering regimes both on growth and yield characteristics.

Conclusion

Mycorrhizal inoculation and watering regime significantly enhanced growth and yield of rice varieties evaluated. Across varieties Igbemo and Benue resulted in enhanced growth and yield. The growth and yield performance were generally affected by watering regime, the 4- day watering interval had enhanced growth and yield compared with the 8- and 12- day watering intervals. Inoculation using ambuscular mycorrhizal fungi improved growth and yield of the rice varieties compared with the non - inoculated. The interactions between variety, watering regime and mycorrhizal inoculation were significant on most of the growth and yield characters measured. The 8- day and 12- day watering intervals appeared to have been long enough time for watering and resulted in soil moisture deficit stress condition for rice. The rice varieties evaluated had different

responses to watering regime – enhanced root zone moisture status. Igbemo and Benue varieties had the best performance across the watering intervals. Therefore, the application of mycorrhizal to rice plant promoted effective and good growth and yield and appeared to have alleviated soil moisture deficit constraints to growth in rice plants. Policy makers should take the initiative to inform and educate farmers on the importance and the use of biofertilizers, AMF particularly in soil water management practices should be promoted for adoption by farmers.

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